

water (10 ml) with stirring. The solution was refluxed to get a clear solution. 2-Hydroxy-4-naphthaldehyde (1.0 g) dissolved in acetone was then added to it and the mixture was left in cold dark place. The resulting solid was washed several times with water, crystallised from acetone and dried in air, m.p. 274°.

Preparation of metal complexes: All the metal complexes were prepared by reacting the aqueous solution of metal ion (0.02 M) and acetone solution of ligands (0.02 M) in appropriate proportions in presence of a little dilute sulphuric acid. The reaction mixture was digested on a water-bath and the resulting solid was then washed with hot water and dried in air. All the complexes were found to be stable upto 110–20° (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Ni	C	H	N
Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂)·H ₂ O	19.35 (19.33)	47.40 (47.41)	3.60 (3.62)	13.81 (13.82)
Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ OS)·H ₂ O	18.35 (18.36)	45.01 (45.04)	3.42 (3.40)	13.10 (13.13)
Pd(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂)	30.25 (30.27)	40.96 (40.97)	3.13 (3.17)	11.92 (11.95)
Pd(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ OS)	28.91 (28.96)	39.15 (38.96)	2.96 (2.99)	11.42 (11.43)

Results and Discussion

It is known⁹ that thiosemicarbazones coordinate through S and N¹ (>C=N¹-N²H-C(=X)-N³<). The ir spectra of the complexes show the coordination through N¹ and sulphur or oxygen. The ν_{NH} ligand band remains practically unchanged in the complexes showing that N² and N³ do not take part in the coordination. The formation of M-S bond is substantiated by the decrease in $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ from 710 (ligand) to 600 cm⁻¹ (complexes). The presence of new bands at 400–500 cm⁻¹ indicates coordination through N, O and S in the complexes.

The bands at 350–3490br cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{OH} stretching, 730–800 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the rocking mode and 1590–1600 cm⁻¹ due to H-O-H bending mode, indicate the presence of coordinated water in the complexes. The square-planar structure of these complexes is indicated from their diamagnetism and electronic spectral band (13000–14500 cm⁻¹).

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N-2-Hydroxynaphthalylidene-o-aminophenol Complexes of some Tripositive Rare Earth Metal Ions

G. B. EL-HEFNAWY*, S. H. ETAIW, A. K. T. MAKY**

and

S. A. M. ISMAIL

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt

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THE present work describes an investigation of the complexes formed by the hydrated lanthanide(III) chlorides with N-2-hydroxynaphthalylidene-o-aminophenol (LH₂).

Experimental

The ligand (LH₂) was prepared by the recommended method¹, m.p. 186°. The hydrated lanthanide chlorides were prepared by the standard method² and then dissolved in absolute ethanol. Ethanol, DMF, nitromethane and nitrobenzene were purified by the recommended methods^{1,3}.

Lanthanone complexes were prepared as follows. A mixture of LH₂ (2 mmol), piperidine (2 mmol) and hydrated lanthanide chloride (1 mmol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 30 min. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum dessicator over fused CaCl₂. The solid complexes decompose at 320–600° without melting. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The physical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁴.

** El-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt.

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
La ₃ L ₃ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Pale yellow	48.8 (49.1)	3.5 (3.6)	3.9 (4.0)	28.0 (28.2)
Nd ₃ L ₃	Pale yellow	51.4 (51.0)	2.6 (2.9)	4.4 (4.2)	28.3 (28.4)
Sm ₃ L ₃	Yellow	48.4 (48.3)	2.6 (2.8)	4.2 (4.3)	31.4 (31.0)
Gd ₃ L ₃ . ⁻ C ₂ H ₅ OH	Pale yellow	49.2 (49.6)	4.0 (3.8)	4.3 (4.1)	30.3 (30.2)
Dy ₃ L ₃ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Yellow	48.8 (49.0)	3.6 (3.7)	4.1 (4.0)	31.4 (31.0)
Ho ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	45.6 (45.9)	3.4 (3.4)	3.5 (4.1)	32.3 (32.2)
Er ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	44.6 (45.0)	3.5 (3.4)	3.8 (4.0)	32.3 (32.2)
Yb ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Pale yellow	43.9 (44.5)	3.3 (3.3)	3.6 (4.0)	32.5 (32.9)
Lu ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Pale yellow	44.9 (44.6)	3.5 (3.6)	4.0 (4.1)	33.4 (33.7)
Y ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	52.5 (53.0)	3.8 (3.9)	4.5 (4.8)	30.1 (30.1)

Results and Discussion

The ir and ¹H nmr spectra of LH₂ show evidence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the OH stretching vibration appearing as a broad band centred at 2 720 cm⁻¹ and with a broad signal at δ 9.65 \pm 0.1. The ir band at 3 450 cm⁻¹ and the signal at δ 7.1 \pm 0.1 are characteristics of the benzal OH group. The signals at δ 9.65 and 7.10 disappear on deuteration with D₂O. The azomethine proton exhibits a sharp signal at δ 8.75 and a sharp ir band at 3 065 cm⁻¹. Two absorption bands at 355 and 430 nm were observed in the electronic spectra of LH₂. They suffered a blue-shift on complexation indicating the covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds which increases as the atomic number increases. The correlation between the long wavelength band and the atomic number of the crystal radius gives excellent linear relationships for the metals beyond Gd^{III}. The presence of the water or ethanol molecules in these complexes is evident by a broad band at 3 400 - 3 500 cm⁻¹, the appearance of a medium to weak band at 2 920 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of ethanol in the ir spectra of the complexes and by the appearance of sharp signal at δ 3.4 \pm 0.05 in the nmr spectra of the complexes. The bands due to the OH group at 2 720 and 3 450, δ_{OH} at 1 370 and ν_{OH} at 940 cm⁻¹, disappear in the ir spectra of the complexes. The bands due to ν_{OH} , ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-N} shifted to shorter frequencies while ν_{C-O} shifted to higher frequency for the complexes than those observed in the ir spectrum of the ligand.

Also, both signals at δ 7.1 and 9.65 corresponding to the ligand OH groups disappear in the ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes of La^{III} and Lu^{III}. On the other hand, the signal due to the azomethine

proton slightly shifted up-field at δ 8.75 - 8.94. Thus, we can conclude that both OH groups and the nitrogen atom are involved in the coordination sphere.

The thermogravimetric study showed that the water and ethanol molecules in the complexes are coordinated to the lanthanide ion and are not just a part of the crystal lattice.

The molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in dimethyl formamide, nitrobenzene and nitromethane were in the range 70 - 87 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹. Thus, these complexes are strong electrolytes type⁵ under the experimental conditions used.

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Complexation of Dimethyltin(IV) Ion with 2-Mercaptopyridine-N-oxide and 8-Hydroxyquinoline-N-oxide

KH. AJIT SINGH and V. D. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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IN continuation of our previous study on the complexation behaviour of dialkyltin(IV) ions¹ we report here the stability constants and related thermodynamic parameters of complex formation of dimethyltin(IV) ion with 2-mercaptopyridine-N-oxide and 8-hydroxyquinoline-N-oxide (hereafter 2MPNO and 8HQNO respectively) at 20, 30 and 40° in 75% (v/v) dioxan-water at a fixed ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$).

Experimental

Experimental details of pH titration procedure are the same as described earlier¹. The ligands 2MPNO and 8HQNO (Aldrich) and dimethyltin dichloride (Alfa) were used. The acid dissociation constants of the ligands and formation constants of the complexes were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti². The thermodynamic para-